

The importance of innovative technologies in teaching English

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Abstract: This article highlights the great importance given to foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the innovative technologies necessary for learning them.

Key words: Foreign language, game, innovative technology, technological tools, methods, methods

After our country gained independence, interest in teaching foreign languages increased and many opportunities were created for young people. As our first president Islam Karimov said, "Currently, teaching foreign languages is given great importance in our country. This is certainly not for nothing. Today, there is no need to overestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our countries, which are striving to take their rightful place in the world community, for our people, who are building their great future in solidarity and cooperation with our foreign partners. As a logical continuation of these thoughts, the Presidential Decree "On measures to further improve the system of teaching foreign languages" adopted on December 10, 2012 expanded the opportunities for learning foreign languages. In our republic, new methods and requirements have been developed in accordance with the recommendations of the European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) for foreign language teaching and assessment of knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers. According to it, textbooks were created for students of general

education schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language is increasing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, speaking, listening and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them. Educational technologies are effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process. It also provides for increasing the quality and efficiency of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is incomparable. The use of technological tools is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, reading, listening and speaking). For example, in order to listen and understand, of course, this process cannot be carried out without a computer, player, CD discs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. At the same time, the reader is required to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, adherence to grammatical rules, vocabulary and its meanings. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in the educational process is that students know information and communication technologies well and are able to use them. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most fruitful ways.

In this process, among other things: - when using computers, the student can watch and listen to foreign language videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons; - it is possible to listen and watch foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs; - use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are considered a more traditional method; - CD players can be used. The use of these technical

tools makes the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students [1]. Today, teaching through interactive games is becoming a tradition in schools. It is known that the lesson is conducted on the basis of various games, which ensures that students demonstrate their capabilities, concentrate, improve their knowledge and skills, and become stronger.

The basis of the use of game technology is the activity that activates and accelerates the student. According to psychologists, the psychological mechanisms of playful activity rely on the fundamental needs of a person to express himself, find a stable place in life, self-control, and realize his potential. Any game should be based on generally accepted educational principles and tactics. Educational games should be based on educational subjects. In the process of games, the student is more interested in this activity than in a regular lesson and works freely. It should be noted that the game is, first of all, a method of teaching. Pupils participate in game lessons with interest, strive to win, and the teacher also provides education to the pupil through them. The student believes that he can speak, listen, understand, and write in English while playing games, he is interested [2]. We know that in the current educational process, the student should be the subject. Focusing more on interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English language classes is to teach students to think independently. Today, English language teachers are using the following innovative methods based on the experience of pedagogues in the United States of America and England: - "Creative Problem Solving" to use this method, the beginning of the story is read and how it ends. the judgment of students is referred to; - "Merry Riddles" teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, they learn unfamiliar words and find the answer to riddles; - "Quick answers" helps to increase the efficiency of the lesson; - "Chigil yazdi" ("Warm-up exercises") use various

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